

Climate Change: Temperature Rise and Water Scarcity.

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Abstract

Climate change is exacerbating both water scarcity and water related hazards such as floods and drought. Climate change as well as human factors is increasingly denying children their right to safe water and sanitation. Burning fossil fuels, cutting down forests and farming live stocks influence climate and earth's temperature. This adds enormous amounts of greenhouse gases to those naturally occurring in the atmosphere increasing the green house effect and global warming. Increasing temperature disrupts precipitation pattern and entire water cycle and moving entire living population into a dry well. According to recent updates of weather Varanasi in UP reached about 47.2 degree equals 140 years record (Times of India. May 29, 2024). Similar is the case with Jhansi 49 degree and Delhi around 50 degree. About two billion people worldwide do not have access to safe drinking water today (SDG2022), and roughly half of the world's population is experiencing severe water scarcity for at least part of the year. These numbers are expected to increase, aggravated by climate change and population growth. Climate change has made extreme weather events such as floods and drought was likely and more severe. Water related disasters have dominated the list of disasters over the past 50 years and account for 70% of all deaths related to natural disasters (World Bank). Since 2000 flood related disasters have been raised by 134 % and drought related disasters increased by 29%. Over the same period most droughts related deaths occurred in Africa. Half of the world's population could be living in areas facing water scarcity by as early as 2025. Some 700 million people could be displaced by intense water scarcity by 2030. It is very unfortunate to know that by 2040, roughly 1 in 4 children worldwide will be living in area of extremely high water stress.

Keywords

Water, Climate Change, Rainfall, Ice Sheets, Rising Sea Levels, Floods and Droughts .

Introduction

Water and climate change are inseparable. Climate change affects the world's water in complex ways. From unpredictable rainfall patterns to shrinking ice sheets, rising sea levels, floods and droughts are most adverse impact of climate change on water. Rising global temperature increase the moisture the atmosphere can hold, resulting in more storms and heavy rains, but ironically also more intense dry spells as more water evaporates from the land and global weather pattern change. As of the date of writing this i.e. 2026-04-27, north UP is experiencing extremely hot and dry condition with temperature in many areas crossing the 40 to 43 degrees; as the summer will advance there will be scarcity of water in many areas.

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Objective of study

With this work, the author aims to study the effect of climate change on temperature rise and water scarcity, by investigating the relationship between rising global temperature and water-related disasters. This is accomplished by identifying and understanding urban water crises, such as Bengaluru, Chennai, and Noida.

Review of Literature

1. Environment: Problems and Solutions. By D.K.Asthana and Meera Asthana.

Asthana and Asthana's book provides a comprehensive overview of environmental challenges, from pollution and deforestation, to water scarcity. The authors highlight the relationship of ecological systems and urban expansion, showing how human activities can accelerate environmental degradation. Their work also emphasizes the urgent need for sustainable

resource management, especially with respect to India's growing population and erratic distribution of natural resources. The book highlights the importance of policy changes, public awareness, etc. in mitigating environmental problems.

2. A textbook of plant Ecology: A Textbook of Plant Ecology by R.S.Chandel.

Chandel's textbook provides a detailed explanation of ecological principles, focusing on the interaction between plants and their environment. It highlights the role of abiotic factors like soil, water, and climate in shaping plant communities and ecological succession. The author's work shows how human activities such as deforestation and industrialisation, disrupt natural ecological balances and contribute to resource scarcity. Lastly, the book is significant in that it establishes the importance of water as a limiting factor in plant growth and ecosystem stability.

3. Vaidyanathan A.,1994 Water resources : what we do not know. In the Hindu Survey of Environment 1994, Madras.

Vaidyanathan's essay critically examines the gap in knowledge and management of India's water resources, establishing that scarcity is often a result of poor governance rather than absolute shortage. In furtherance of this, he highlights the uneven distribution of water across regions and the lack of reliable data on groundwater reserves, which complicates effective planning. The author shows how rapid urbanisation and agricultural expansion have intensified demand, whereas traditional water harvesting practices have been neglected.

Main Text

According to recent updates of weather Varanasi in UP reached about 47.2 degrees equals 140 years record (Times of India, May 29, 2024). Similar is the case with Jhansi at 49 degrees and Delhi around 50 degrees.

About two billion people worldwide do not have access to safe drinking water today (SDG Report 2022), and roughly half of the world's population is experiencing severe water scarcity for at least part of the year. These numbers are expected to increase, aggravated by climate change and population growth. Climate change has also increased the likelihood or severity of drought events in many parts of the world, causing reduced agricultural yields, drinking water shortages, increased wildfire risk, loss of lives and economic damages. Drought and flood risks and associated societal damages are projected to further increase with every degree of global warming.

Climate change has made extreme weather events such as floods and drought not only more likely, but also more severe. Water related disasters have dominated the list of disasters over the past 50 years and account for 70% of all deaths related to natural disasters (World Bank).

Since 2000 flood related disasters have been raised by 134 % and drought related disasters increased by 29%. Over the same period, most droughts related deaths occurred in Africa. It was estimated that half of the world's population could be living in areas facing water scarcity by as early as 2025. Some 700 million people could be displaced by intense water scarcity by 2030. It is very unfortunate to know that by 2040, roughly 1 in 4 children worldwide will be living in areas of extremely high water stress.

We have a huge quantity of fresh water on our planet but most of it is useless for us as it contains lots of salt in it. Even in countries with adequate water resources water scarcity is very common. Several factors are responsible for water scarcity like collapsed infrastructure contamination or poor management of water resources.

In recent experiences it is clear that climate change, as well as human factors are increasingly denying children their right to safe water and sanitation.

Like other natural resources, global fresh water sources also have their own limitations according to recent studies the total volume of water on earth is estimated at 1.386 billion cubic kilometres, with 97.5% being salt water and 2.5% being fresh water. Of the fresh water 0.3% is in liquid form on the surface. There is a final limit up to which mankind can withdraw water available in various deposits on Earth's crust, without damaging the natural resource base or without causing any adverse change in the environment around.

Out of the 3% fresh water available, only 1.2% can be used as drinking water. The rest is locked up in glaciers ice caps, or buried deep in the ground. Most of our drinking water comes from rivers and streams. Of all the water on earth more than 99% of earth's water is unusable by humans and many other living organisms.

The ill-effects of withdrawing more water than the total utilizable water may be drastic, thus becoming central to the horrors of water scarcity.

Major Causes of Water Scarcity

The main causes of water scarcity are as follows,

1. Climate change and rise in temperature.
2. Natural calamities such as droughts and floods.
3. Increased human consumption and lack of water harvesting systems.
4. Overuse and wastage of water.
5. A global rise in freshwater demand.
6. Overuse of water bodies and its consequent slow recharge.
7. Rapid urbanisation and industrialisation.
8. Inefficient agricultural practices.

Climate change worsens the situation causing irregular rainfall patterns and affecting the recharge of rivers and aquifers. This is where one can observe the ill-effects of the withdrawal of more water than is necessary. In absence of rains, it is the water table below which sustains natural plant growth and keeps Earth's surface moist and humid. With the receding water table, agriculture suffered a lot and the process of desertification had started.

Drought and rains badly affect fresh water supply especially in a country like ours where there is no proper drainage and proper water harvesting systems.

Causes of Floods

1. Excessive rainfall poor drainage system and lack of effective infrastructure during heavy rain.
2. Overflowing of the rivers.
3. Collapsed dams.
4. Snowmelt.
5. Deforestation and changing climate.
6. Emission of green house gases.
7. Rise in temperature and melting of glaciers.

Similarly human activities can also help trigger droughts, such as

1. Cutting down of trees.
2. Deforestation reduces the soil ability to hold water.
3. Desertification of the land due to drought.
4. Drying out of land due to various industries and tests.

According to a survey the domestic water consumption under normal condition in an Indian city is 135 litres per head per day, with respect to drinking, cooking, bathing, washing of clothes, and other household chores.

According to a rough estimate, to produce 20 tons of organic matter in terms of fresh weight, at least 2000 tons of water has to be provided to the roots. Most of which is lost in transpiration following agriculture, power generation and industries are the biggest consumer of fresh water. Navigation, fisheries, hydroelectric power plants, recreational activities also require a huge quantity of water, much of which flows down to the seas.

There is no proper water harvesting system such as that in ancient times. The local methods of harvesting water include tanks ponds and wells. Crescent shaped earthen embankments and check dams were the structures used during ancient water harvesting. For instance, techniques like the *Tankas* or *Kunds* in ancient Rajasthan were so sustainable, they could hold enough drinking water for 5-6 family members for entire season. In other areas where similar practice continues, rainwater fills up the ponds near the ancient water harvest structures that hold water during the monsoons.

In 2001, Tamil Nadu became the first Indian state to make rainwater harvesting compulsory in every building to avoid groundwater depletion. In Rajasthan, rainwater harvesting has traditionally been practised by the people of the Thar Desert, as previously highlighted.

For almost all kind of human activity more water is drawn than what is actually needed. Much of the surplus water is returned back in impure state. If we use our water judiciously, we can

avoid over-consumption. Being human we have the tendency to waste water because of its easy availability. If a water meter is installed and money was charged for every bucket of water, such consumption will drastically decline.

In our country water resources are not distributed evenly, some localities have plenty of water others have little of it, owed to the erratic nature of rainfall in the subcontinent. Therefore, transport of water from one place to another becomes an essential part of water conservation efforts. Many river basins have plenty of water which flows down unused to the seas, surplus water could therefore be diverted to drier regions through a system of canals and pipes. Pollution spoils huge quantities of our surface water so some kind of purifying treatment should be undertaken instead of releasing it in to our surface water, if not for direct consumption these waters can be used satisfactorily for other purposes such as washing and cleaning, as coolant in industries, for irrigation, etc.

When it comes to the human experience of water scarcity, the term is divided in to two categories; firstly, physical water scarcity and secondly, economic water scarcity. Physical water scarcity refers to a lack of available of water resources in comparison to demand and economic water scarcity is a result of insufficient water access due to financial issues.

Due to increasing population and development of various housing schemes we hardly get plain land which can absorb water and make access to ground water. There is concrete jungle all around the city so rain water gets wasted. There is little concept of water harvesting.

RO water purifiers are undoubtedly the most popular and widely used purification system, but for every one litre of filtered water, an average RO purifier wastes around three litres of water. This indicates that just 25% water gets cleaned and rest 75% of water is wasted.

The *Bengaluru Water Crisis* is an intriguing example here; Bengaluru, India's third most populated city is facing severe water crisis. The garden city of India once had multiple lakes which are artificially made. In the 1960, there were over 280 lakes in the city, yet only a handful of them exist today. Most of them were encroached upon as the city expanded rapidly since it became the Information Technology (IT) hub.

Today the city's ground water is being exploited limitlessly as the Cauvery and Arkavati Rivers cannot provide enough water to meet 2600 million litres' daily requirement of the city.

Another example is of the *Chennai Water Crisis*; In 2019 there was a water crisis occurring in India most notably in the coastal city of Chennai in Tamil Nadu. On 19th June 2019, Chennai city officially declared that day Zero when almost no water is left had been reached, as well as the four main reservoirs supplying water to the city had run dry. Supply of water was again halted on February 28, 2024, due to the lack of inflow from the Meltur Dam pushing the reservoir in to the dead storage.

Lastly, the *Noida Water Crisis* highlights the plight of the Residents of Noida and Greater Noida who have been facing a severe water crisis with some housing societies resorting to hiring private water tankers to meet their daily drinking water demands.

All major cities in India are facing the same crisis. Now, the responsibility is inadvertently on the citizens of the country to cope with these disasters by devising ways to use piped water optimally.

Over the past few weeks, households in Bangalore have gone the extra mile to save water. Installation of rainwater harvesting systems, water rationing with smart metres that cut off the water supply beyond a certain limit, active bore well recharging techniques, water pressure control through faucets and bathroom fittings among others.

Solutions for such Problems

Healthy aquatic ecosystems and improved water management can lower greenhouse gas emissions and provide protection against climate hazards.

Wetlands also serve as a buffer against extreme weather events. They provide natural shield against storms and absorb excess water and precipitation.

Early warning systems for floods, droughts, and other water related issues can reduce disaster risk.

Water supply and sanitation systems that can withstand climate change could save the lives of many infants every year.

Climate smart agriculture agricultures using drip irrigation and other means of using water more efficiently can help reduce demand on freshwater supplies.

Conclusion

Water scarcity limits access to safe water for drinking and for practicing basic hygiene at home, in schools and in health care facilities. When water is scarce, sewage system can fail and the threat of contracting diseases like cholera surges.

While water scarcity is predominately a man made creation, humans also have the capacity to develop solutions to mitigate the increase in water scarcity. In certain districts of Rajasthan, authorities have successfully constructed over 184,000 reinforced *Taankas* since 2016. Rain water harvesting system were well developed in ancient times, Amber fort built about three centuries ago is a classic example of such a system; Here for instance, systems such as *Mansingh Mahal ka Tanka* collect roof runoff and can hold an approximate of 300,000 litres.

According to UNICEF, at least two-thirds of the world's population which is a total of about four billion people, already live with severe water scarcity for at least one month each year.

The situation is so severe that the World Economic Forum says that water problems must be solved because it's one of the top risks to humanity and human economics. The people most vulnerable to water scarcity today live in India and China, two of the most populated countries in the world. But the water demand and water quality problems also affect dozens of other countries including Great Britain, Australia, Mexico, Yemen, Iran, Pakistan, Saudi Arabia, countries throughout sub-Saharan Africa, and the United States. As the water scarcity becomes complex and varies so widely across countries and regions UNICEF works at multiple levels to increase access to safe water, such as

1. Identifying new water resources.
2. Improving the efficiency of water resources.
3. Planning for Rural and Urban Scarcity.
4. Expanding technologies to ensure climate resilience.
5. Changing behaviours.
6. Planning national water needs.
7. Supporting the wash sector.
8. Strict action against misuse of water resources.

In India, people only seem to care when something directly affects them; likewise, these talks of "Saving Water" are only acted upon when the situation becomes dire.

Government could take action only if there is any rule exists. Wastage or misuse of potable ground water will now be a punishable offence in India. A directive of the Central Ground Water Authority (CGWA) says violators will face imprisonment up to five years or fine which may extend to Rs one lakh, or with both, for non compliance of a mechanism to be framed by local civic bodies to implement the order.

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